

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10889964>

Abstract; *Teaching a foreign language can be challenging since students need to take into account the cultural distinctions between their native language and the language they are trying to learn. Foreign language teachers should try to find new ways to teach it effectively. So every teacher knows that there is no best method to teach because day by day new contributions are being made. Thus, especially, a foreign language teacher has to know and use at least one or more methods in language teaching.*

Keywords: *foreign language, innovative educational technologies, competencies, psychological and pedagogical technologies, personality-oriented technologies, case technologies, standard of education.*

We live in a global world, it influences simultaneously on evolving of language as English. Nowadays this language is getting paramount in every corner of the world.

Nowadays, the process of innovative changes of educational system activity continues. Modern requirements are applied for modernization in the education system. Thus, this phase is called modernization era of educational system. Today, while implementing the third phase of National program of preparing cadres, all new specialists undergoing the higher educational system are required to know one or several foreign languages. In connection with this, huge tasks are set before teachers of English language. The main subjects of educational reforms are assigned teachers. Therefore, if a teacher is ready to implement new pedagogical innovations, he can provide purposeful introduction of innovative ideas into educational process. Lately, the length of significant official acts was issued on improving and augmenting the foreign languages teaching.

Communicative Language Teaching [CLT] was introduced to develop pupils' four skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing in a communicative context in Uzbekistan. CLT focuses mainly classroom activities, which based on communicative methods like group work, task-work, and filling the information gap. The issue of English language learning in primary section is a very important phenomenon for pupils. English language is taught in the primary levels to improve the basic knowledge on a foreign language. A host of variables comes into play an important role in determining the issue, which may vary from one context to another. It may be difficult to make a complete list of the variables, however, some of them are lack of proficiency of the teacher, attitudes of the pupils, socio-cultural background, and in particular, language learning policy itself.[3, 156]

The main purpose of using language is to communicate one's needs, necessities, feelings, thoughts and ideas to others. An important factor in the study of a foreign language by young children is the playful moment of learning, since the child is a child, and if he is taught by the usual program even at the initial stage of it, he will soon be tired and lose interest in the language being studied. This can cause a long aversion to the subject and for all subsequent years of training, so it is very important to plan the educational process correctly, relying on the psychological and physical characteristics of this age.

But one cannot rely solely on games, since modernity, the expansion of cultural boundaries, the desire for knowledge of the world in primary school children causes them the

practical importance of learning English. Many children already from the first grade of the school want to become translators to "travel to different countries" or "earn a lot", and by the end of the school these children tend to want to become philologists in order to understand the language more deeply.

The role of the imitation process is not really as great as it might seem at first glance. Children are already consciously approaching the study of English, so the impact of imitation is reduced.

It is useful to use the manuals in which the culture and traditions of England are covered in an accessible way in order to raise children's interest to studying languages. These are three priorities of teaching English in primary school:

- teaching which is based on the skills and instincts children bring with them to the classroom;

-the development of attitudes and responses which contribute to the process of developing competence in another language;

-ways of working with the language for real.

If we take these priorities seriously then we are obviously no longer talking about classrooms where the children spend all their time sitting still in rows or talking only to the teacher. We are also talking about teaching which will sometimes involve teachers in adapting the textbook or in devising activities of their own. In both respects we need to be realistic.

Communicative approach to language teaching is one of the most effective in the process of teaching primary school children. But teachers can try to become more informed on other approaches and methods which they feel only begin to appear in development of the second language of students and provide some guidance in instruction in use of these forms at that moment to see if any benefits are made. It can be useful to stimulate pupils to participate in process, make actions which draw attention of pupils to forms which they use in communicative practice, develop contexts in which they can provide feedback and encourage them to ask questions.

Decisions on when and how to use distinctive methods depends on the skills of teacher and teaching situation. Absolutely different approaches should be used with the fourth or fifth grade language pupils, small children beginning to learn second language, immigrant who isn't able to read and write in the language and the teenager learning foreign language at school.

It is possible to claim that many teachers are well informed on need to keep balance of form-focus and meaning-focus methods to concentrate attention and that can just mean that recommendations based on research confirmed the existing practice in class. Though it can be right somehow, it is difficult to say that all teachers approach their task with clear understanding of how it is better to achieve the objectives. It is not always easy to stop using ordinal methods and say: "It is interesting, is it really the most effective way to go about it." Besides, many teachers do not want to practice in class methods which are contrary to the prevailing tendency among the colleagues or in their educational contexts, and are not present any doubts that many teachers still work in environments where there is an emphasis on accuracy which practically excludes spontaneous language use in class. At the same time, there are proofs that introduction of communicative methods of teaching languages sometimes leads to full refusal of attention to education and corrections of mistakes in teaching second language.[2,56]

All methods can yield good results if they are used according to certain class or the level of knowledge of pupils or the atmosphere in a class.

Whenever method you would follow, it is important to be convinced that your pupils receive as much time as it is possible to communicate. Therefore it is very important to include work in small groups or pairs as part of your lessons. It gives pupils much more time to speak English during lessons.

The only possibly novel approach to the material is in its organization, namely, by language proficiency level, but the rationale for this organization is unclear. There are some principles for teaching speaking at the three levels. However, a look at these principles shows that they are broad enough to apply at all three levels, and it remains unclear how the author has determined these delineations. "Encourage learners to take reasonable risks in speaking English" falls under the advanced learner principles, but surely a case could be made for encouraging that advice at all levels. Similarly, the intermediate level principle "Personalize the speaking activities whenever possible" could apply as well to beginner and advanced learners. Altogether, there is tremendous overlap in material. This is confusing for the reader.

Particularly with adult learners, even at a beginner proficiency level, it is good practice to introduce self-evaluation (perhaps in a simpler format than the book illustrates) so that learners develop independence in their language learning from the start. Similarly, the explanations of different kinds of speaking tests (placement, diagnostic, progress, achievement) appear in the "beginner" chapter even though this information is relevant at all language proficiency levels. The same type of overlap is apparent with the description of activity types across levels. For instance, all three sections include picture-based activities. Bailey is perhaps attempting to show scaffolding, (i.e., how the same activity type can be applied at different levels by building on existing knowledge), but this is not explicit. It might have been clearer to organize the material by activity type and illustrate how one concept can be applied at different levels.[1, 145]

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